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**OTHERNESS AND THE CULTURE OF CANCELLATION
AS OPPOSITION TO THE ETHICS OF CARE ON THE
EXAMPLE OF «CONFESSIONS OF A HÉTÉROSEXUEL
LÉGÈREMENT DÉPASSÉ» BY FRÉDÉRIC BEIGBEDER**

Bohdan PARAMONOV

(V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University, Ukraine)

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0613-5761>

Bohdan Paramonov. Otherness and the culture of Cancellation as opposition to the ethics of Care on the example of ‘Confessions of a heterosexual Legerement Depasse’ by Frédéric Beigbeder. The article examines the concept of “otherness” as a key element in understanding eco-feminism and the “ethics of care” in modern literature and society. Tracing its historical development from ancient myths to today, the study highlights how encounters with the “Other” shape identity and social structures. Contemporary marginalised groups, including women, people of colour, and LGBTQ+ communities, emphasize the relevance of discussions on inequality and discrimination. The “cancel culture” phenomenon influences social boundaries, political correctness, and self-censorship, shaping identity and discourse. Frédéric Beigbeder’s autobiographical novel “Confessions d’un hétérosexuel légèrement dépassé” explores identity and otherness, raising questions about censorship, political correctness, and social dynamics. His work prompts critical reflection on modern social discourse and identity formation.

Keywords: *otherness, identity, cancel culture, political correctness, self-censorship, gender inequality, contemporary French literature, Frédéric Beigbeder, autobiographical novel, Confessions d’un hétérosexuel légèrement dépassé.*

Throughout history, the concepts of “Self” and “Other” have been opposed, leading to feelings of superiority and exclusion. The encounter with the “Other” reflects the

complex relationship between one's identity and the perception of the other, touching on understanding, empathy, and social barriers.

In myths, religious texts, and epics, the confrontation between the hero and the «Other» emphasized the idea of separation. Colonialism reinforced this view by creating prejudice against other cultures. Postmodern literature sees this concept as a means of perpetuating and revising traditional perceptions.

Since the mid-twentieth century, “otherness” has become a key theme in the humanities. According to Derek Attridge, the term was already widely used in 1999. It encompasses various aspects of difference, from ethnicity and culture to social status and gender. Simone de Beauvoir's views helped to broaden the concept to include a gender dimension. In any context, “Otherness” is perceived as a challenge to established norms, which requires reflection and response. Thus, otherness is not an objective but the result of perception and identity formation.

In literature, the image of the “Other” is a powerful tool, allowing authors to reveal the diversity of human experience and readers to make sense of it. Contemporary trends increasingly address themes of gender inequality, racism, and migration, which have been facilitated by the voices of marginalised communities – women, writers from non-white and non-European cultures, and LGBTQ+ writers. This broadens the perceptions of the interplay between the “self” and the “Other”.

This shift in perception influenced public attitudes towards the traditional social system and intolerance, causing the formation of the so-called “cult of safety” in US universities and globally. This has led to strict restrictions on speech that could be interpreted as racist, sexist, or transphobic. According to research by Jonathan Haidt and Greg Lukianoff, since the late 2010s, these processes have contributed to the spread of a “cancellation culture”, intensified with the development of social media.

“Cancel culture” is a modern form of social ostracism, where public criticism and boycotts are used to hold people accountable for statements or actions deemed unacceptable. This phenomenon helps a community to set boundaries of what is acceptable and to form a collective identity in opposition to the “Other”. The intersection

of the “cancel culture” with the notion of otherness sparks discussions about accountability, opportunities for personal growth, and the challenges of dialogue in a digital world.

Writers who have confronted this phenomenon include Joanne Rowling, accused of transphobia over comments about gender identity; Janine Cummins, whose book “American Dirt” sparked controversy over its depiction of Mexicans; and Orson Scott Card, who was criticized for portraying LGBT characters in a negative way.

French writer Frédéric Beigbeder, known for his provocative prose, explores themes of otherness through criticism of society. In “*99 Francs*”, he denounces consumer culture and its influence on identity formation. In “*Windows on the World*”, through the prism of the events of 11 September, he shows the crisis of identity in the face of catastrophe. “*Un roman français*” is an autobiographical reflection on social amnesia and its impact on identity.

Frédéric Beigbeder's work has always been characterised by satire and black humour, beginning with his early works, such as “*Mémoires d'un jeune homme dérangé*”, and up to his latest scandalous book “*Confessions d'un hétérosexuel légèrement dépassé*” (Beigbeder, 2023). The latter provoked a sharp reaction among feminists: during its presentation in Paris, activists staged a protest, waving posters with accusatory slogans and painting the “Mollat” bookshop.

The occasion for writing the book, according to Frédéric Beigbeder, was an incident in 2018 when his house, car, and allotment were vandalised with offensive graffiti, including the inscription “A rapist lives here.” The author attributes this to the fact that he signed the “343 salauds (scum)” petition, condemned by feminists for the phrase “*Touche pas à ma pute (Don't touch my slut)*” and protesting against the ban on buying sex. Frédéric Beigbeder claims he only meant to criticise the law, which he believes was passed without sufficient debate.

Frédéric Beigbeder, in his book, raises the topic of self-censorship and the impact of political correctness on literature. He argues that a writer should be free to express his

thoughts and experiences, even if someone dislikes his works: “Moralising the world is fine, but sterilising literature is not” (Beigbeder, 2023, p. 15).

Frédéric Beigbeder also believes that his “cancellation” is due to his provocative writing and open discussion of uncomfortable topics. He sees the attack on his house in 2018 as one of the consequences of his honesty: “I think if teenage terrorists attacked my house at night, one of the reasons is that my job is to write and read” (Beigbeder, 2023, p. 15).

The author touches on the topic of privilege and modern identity. As some “white male, born into the bourgeois milieu of the 1960s”, he claims that he did not choose his social position or the color of his skin and does not understand why he is now perceived as the embodiment of injustice. In the book's first section, he even calls himself a victim, emphasising that political correctness has become an instrument of censorship, stifling creativity and freedom of expression.

Frédéric Beigbeder recognises the existence of sexism and harassment, especially in the fashion, film and television industries with which he is associated. In his satirical works, he raised this topic even before the #MeToo movement. However, it was one of his works – a chapter of “*Confessions d'un hétérosexuel légèrement dépassé*” entitled “Un désir effrayant (A fearful desire)” – that led to public condemnation of the writer and attempts to “cancel” him.

Feminist activists reacted strongly to the author's statements, accusing him of justifying sexism and indifference to the problem of violence. In response, Frédéric Beigbeder emphasised that his works have always raised important social issues and spoken out against injustice long before the #MeToo debacle. In his defence, he cited a case in which he testified in a harassment case in defence of injured journalist Tristane Banon. However, critics consider his postings superfluous, disagreeing with his understanding of social problems.

Frédéric Beigbeder is particularly concerned with the topic of violence, which also affects men. He points out that social stereotypes and fear of being ridiculed often prevent them from talking about their own traumas. Despite the lack of research on this topic, he

says that trauma affects everyone, regardless of their status: “We are all victims in some way or another” (Beigbeder, 2023, p. 112).

The concept of “Otherness” has had a significant impact on the formation of literary works and social structures, emphasising the importance of the historical origins and contemporary context of the concept. Frédéric Beigbeder's work “*Confessions d'un hétérosexuel légèrement dépassé*” has become a platform for discussion about gender dynamics and violence. The author draws attention to the problems faced by women, even though his novel contains some provocative ideas and statements. Although the work is the subject of many discussions, it stimulates discussion of social problems and promotes awareness of violence in its various manifestations. The phenomenon of the “cancel culture” raises the issue of the infringement of the rights of certain minority groups, forms of discrimination such as misogyny, racism, violence, etc. and brings to justice those who express and promote such ideas. It is clear that the “cancel culture” should also be regulated with regard to the appropriateness of accusations against certain individuals. All of the above events and reactions emphasise the importance of continuing the dialogue on gender issues and violence in literature and society, helping to raise awareness and promote changes in social norms and stereotypes.

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